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Contributions related to projects ('PgB') Programme Open Science

Project application submission form (Period 2021-2024)

Please fill in one form per project and send it/them until the deadline in electronic form to the following address: open-science@swissuniversities.ch

1. General information

Title and Acronym (short title) of the project :	Open Science for Arts, Design and Music OS-ADM
Primary action line :	Alternative forms of publication
Secondary action line (if applicable) :	Participation to international initiatives
Proposal deadline :	31 May 2021

No	Participating institution(s)
1	Applicant institution <i>SUPSI – Scuola universitaria professionale della Svizzera italiana</i> (leading house)
2	Partner institution <i>FHNW – Fachhochschule Nordwestschweiz</i>
3	Partner institution <i>HES-SO – Haute École Spécialisée de Suisse Occidentale (ECAL, EDHEA, HEAD)</i>
4	Partner institution <i>HKB – Hochschule der Künste Bern</i>
5	Partner institution <i>HSLU – Hochschule Luzern Design & Kunst</i>
6	Partner institution <i>ZHdK – Zürcher Hochschule der Künste</i>

Total project costs

CHF 798'460.–

Total federal contribution requested

CHF 348'460.–

Distribution of the federal contribution by participating institution

SUPSI: CHF 348'460.–

Start and end date of project

1st January 2022 – 31st December 2024

Project management

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2. Information specific to the project

Project description (brief summary), max. ½ page¹

The disciplinary fields of Arts (photography, visual and performing arts, such as dance, theatre and cinema), Design (including sub-disciplines such as visual communication, industrial design, fashion design and interaction design) and Music (including sound and aural arts) present a series of complex issues related to the reuse and distribution of artwork and of third parties content under copyright, not accessible in public domain and subject to a series of restrictions. These disciplinary fields produce a wide range of multimedia outputs, they imply action-research and practice-based research, and they collaborate with specialized national Swiss publishing houses. This situation makes the implementation of Open Access in the disciplinary fields of ADM (Arts, Design and Music) particularly complex. At the same time, practices developed within these fields address issues which are relevant in other disciplines. The present project proposal aims at supporting the Swiss disciplinary field of ADM in implementing the swissuniversities Open Access action plan 2021-2024 in collaboration with key stakeholders. More specifically the project involves a network of Swiss schools of ADM and it develops centralised and local services. The centralised service produces guidelines and solutions for a selection of case studies with the support of a legal team, it produces webinars and training for the local staff, it involves Swiss institutions in international networks and it triggers Green and Gold Open Access among the publications in the field of ADM. At a local level, the different schools involved notify case studies, receive training and coaching to support their researchers, teachers and collaborators, to include Open Access and Open Data (i.e. copyright management, open licenses, multimedia formats, reviewing processes) within students' curricula and to negotiate with national publishers specialised in ADM. The project contributes to alternative forms of publications and it participates to international initiatives: it implements in 2022 the guidelines, in 2023 training and coaching, and in 2024 the negotiations with institutional, national and international publishers. Institutions involved: SUPSI (Ticino), HES-SO (ECAL, Lausanne; HEAD – Genève; EDHEA, Valais), ZHdK (Zurich), HSLU Hochschule Luzern – Design & Kunst (Lucerne), BFH (Bern), FHNW (Basel). Letters of support from Swiss Federal Office of Culture, Pro Helvetia Swiss Arts Council, Swiss National Science Foundation, DARIAH-EU Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities, SARN Swiss Artistic Research Network, SDN Swiss Design Network.

¹ This abstract will be published on the Open Science Program Public Website

Project content and objectives

A) Objectives and Pertinence, max. 5 pages

What are the objectives of your project (please make them SMART)?

The proposal aims at supporting the Swiss disciplinary field of ADM in implementing the swissuniversities Open Access Strategy and Action Plan 2021-2024, in collaboration with key stakeholders (see Table 1, below). The project contributes to alternative forms of publications by negotiating with institutional, national and international publishers in the fields of arts, design and music; it participates in international initiatives and it specifically contributes to DARIAH and DOAJ

Specific Objectives	Measurable	Attainable	Relevant	Time-based
- Monitoring of research practices in the field of ADM.	- Collecting information from ADM educational institutions in Switzerland (expecting 20 case studies, with a selection of 10).	- Involvement of a specialised project team.	- The project specific objectives are aligned with the approach defined by the national OA Strategy and Action Plan. They address the specific needs of disciplinary fields with the endowment of the key stakeholders (all Swiss schools of arts and design are involved in the project). They address issues which are relevant also for other disciplines.	- The project is developed within the timeframe of the OA Strategy and Action Plan (2022-2024). It is designed to support the implementation phase of the OA Strategy and Action Plan and to allow institutions to continue in the OA Policy and Open Science approach after the end of the project with their trained local teams and according to guidelines. The project is structured into three main phases: Phase 1 (2022) – Production of the guidelines Phase 2 (2023) – Training and coaching Phase 3 (2024) – Negotiation with national and international publishers and dissemination of the project results. Preparation of the follow up of the project.
- Monitoring of the practices of publishers specialised in ADM in the field of Open Access.	- Review of the publications on DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals) - Networking with DARIAH (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities).	- Involvement of a specialised project team.		
- Providing guidelines to researchers on how to publish in Green and Gold Open Access and deal with common problems.	- Guidelines responding a selection of 10 case studies and to common problems such as the production of multimedia formats in Open Access, the reuse and distribution of artwork and of third parties content under copyright, not accessible in public domain and subject to a series of restrictions; copyright management; use of content under open licenses and release of content under open licenses. - Reviews of the local teams. - 3 webinars	- Training and coaching for trainers. - Support of local teams for researchers in the institutions involved.		
- Including Open Science (i.e. copyright management,	- 3 schools involved in the project organize workshops/seminars/courses related	- Guidelines and webinars provided by the project team.		

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open licenses, multi-media formats, reviewing processes) within students' curricula	to Open Science for their students.	- Support of the project team. - Trained local teams.		
- Implementing Open Access among institutional publications.	- 70% of institutional publications Open Access.	- Training and coaching from the project team. Implementation at a local level with the involvement of the institutions and in accordance with the Open Access policies.		
- Negotiating Open Access with publishers (Green and Gold Road) at a national and international level.	- 3 specialized publishers in art and design with publications in German, French and Italian in Open Access. - 3 international publications in art and design in Open Access.	- Involvement of a specialised project team. - Training and coaching from the project team. - Negotiations based on the relationships of the local teams.		
- Guaranteeing the viability of the project once the funding from the OS programme stops	- All Swiss schools of art and design are involved in the project.	- Project structured in centralised services (2022-2024) and local services (meant to continue after the end of the project). - Training and coaching of local teams. Involvement of Swiss networks for the follow up of the project.		

Table 1. Project objectives (SMART)

Describe the concept and methodology.

The disciplinary fields of Arts (photography, visual and performing arts, such as dance, theatre and cinema), Design (including sub-disciplines such as visual communication, industrial design, fashion design and interaction design) and Music (including sound and aural arts) present a series of complex issues related to the reuse and distribution of artwork and of third parties content under copyright, not accessible in public domain and subject to a series of restrictions. These disciplinary fields produce a wide range of multimedia outputs, they imply action-research and practice-based research, and they collaborate with specialised national Swiss publishers. This situation makes the implementation of Open Access in the disciplinary fields of Arts, Design and Music (ADM) particularly complex. At the same time the practices developed within these fields address issues which are relevant in other disciplines. The project responds to the specific needs related to the implementation of Open Science in the disciplinary fields of ADM, and it provides support through the production of guidelines, training and networking activities aiming at implementing Open Access among national and International publishers.

The project involves a network of Swiss schools of art and design and it develops centralised and local services. The centralised service produces guidelines and solutions for frequent cases with the support of a legal team, it produces webinars and training for the local staff, it involves Swiss institutions in international networks, and it triggers green and gold Open Access among the publications in the field of ADM. At a local level, the different schools involved notify case studies, receive training and coaching to support their researchers, teachers and collaborators, in order to include Open Science (i.e. copyright management, open licenses, multimedia formats, reviewing processes) within students' curricula and to negotiate with national publishers specialised in ADM (see Table 2, annex to the proposal, and Table 3, below).

Activities	Centralised service (project team)	Local services (local teams)
Coordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Production of the reports - Administrative management of the project - Communication within the project, regular meetings - Active involvement of the Swiss schools of ADM 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Definition of a local team - Review of the reports
Guidelines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documentation about research practices in the field of ADM - Analysis of a selection of case studies produced with the support of legal advice (selection of 10 case studies) - Production of guidelines - Editing and publication of the guidelines 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identifying relevant case studies and best practices (expected 20) - Reviewing of the guidelines
Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Production of 3 webinars - Training and coaching to trainers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participating in training - Training and coaching to researchers - 3 schools involved in the project organize workshops/seminars/courses related to Open Science for their students.
National publishers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support and coaching 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Relationships with 3 national specialised publishers in the field of ADM - Implementation of OA on institutional publications (70%)
International publishers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documentation about practices of publishers specialised in ADM in the field of Open Access - Networking with international publishers in the field of ADM to support 5 publications in Open Access - Relationships with DOAJ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Suggesting publication
Communication and dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication and dissemination of the project guidelines and tools at a national and international level - Institutional website with guidelines, recorded webinars and other documents (June 2023) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication and dissemination of the project guidelines and tools within the institution and among researchers and students

Table 3. Activities: centralised service and local services

How does the project meet the objectives of the national OA Strategy and Action Plan?

The project contributes to the implementation of Open Access in Switzerland by 2024 in the fields of ADM, and it is designed to guarantee the prosecution of Open Access after 2024, implemented and supported by the Swiss institutions working in the disciplinary fields. More specifically the project supports institutions and researchers in reaching 100% of scholarly publication activity in Open Access and all scholarly publications funded by public money in the fields of ADM freely accessible on the internet by 2024 (see Table 4, below, and Table 5, below).

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Guiding principles of the OA Strategy	Contribution of the proposal to the objectives of the OA Strategy
1. Powerful and unified approach	The project involves all Swiss schools of art and design to join forces, collaborate and respond to common difficulties in their disciplinary fields. It creates and provides centralised services and it supports the local implementation of Open Access and Open Science in each institution. Furthermore it collaborates with national and international existing networks, initiatives and stakeholders.
2. Support and commitment from research communities	The communication of the project addresses specific targets with different communication tools and different aims. All relevant stakeholders are involved (the Swiss schools of art and design, grant-makers, existing national and international relevant networks and initiatives).
3. Cost transparency and cost neutrality	The project involves the negotiation with 3 national publishers and 3 international publishers, as well as the exploration of new forms of multimedia publications allowing to respond to the needs of research in the fields of ADM.
4. Ascertaining control and diversity of the scientific production process	
5. Revision of quality assessment system	In the guidelines, the project considers the current evaluation process and reputation gain associated with the fields of ADM, which produces action-research and practice-based research, it is characterized by a wide range of multimedia outputs, and it has discipline-specific publishing practices.

Table 4. Contributions of the proposal to the guiding principles of the OA Strategy

Action items of the OA Strategy	Contribution of the proposal to the action items of the OA Strategy
1. Adopting and aligning OA policies	The project relies on the OA policies adopted by the institutions involved, which are already responsible for implementing OA by 2024. Within this project their role is respected, but supported by guidelines and training. Furthermore the project takes into consideration the disciplinary differences, the various kinds of research, and the many ways of disseminating results which characterize the fields of ADM.
2. Negotiations with publishers	The project contributes to the negotiations with publishers in the fields of ADM at a national and international level, and it develops pilot activities by involving at a national level three Swiss publishing houses specialized in ADM and with monographs in particular in German, French and Italian. The negotiations implemented by the project do not address major scientific publishers (current negotiations are already implemented), but it addresses the specific publishers relevant in the fields of ADM which are not addressed by swissuniversities and the national networks: the project contributes to the national strategy in a complementary and specialised approach.
3. Coordinating and pooling resources	The project takes advantage of existing resources, infrastructures (i.e. repositories and services).
4. Alternative form of publishing	The project focuses on alternative forms of publication by implementing Open Access among institutional publications, by involving national and international publishers in Open Access, by supporting Open Access officers, researchers and students in this process of Open Access publishing in the specific fields of ADM with the production of guidelines and training, and by exploring the use of institutional websites as a form of multimedia Open Access research output, applying the FAIR Open Access Publishing.

5. Communicating and rising awareness	The project promotes awareness about Open Access and Open Science specifically in the fields of ADM; it provides training and guidelines for an efficient implementation of Open Access in its specific field. Furthermore, to efficiently communicate and to address its specific targets, the project involves the Swiss networks of artistic and design research (SARN and SDN), the key stakeholders in this field, and the national and international projects connected to its topics.
6. Supportive regulatory framework	Open Access in the fields of ADM is often connected with national and international cultural repositories (archives, database of images, artworks, data repositories), and it depends on international legislations related to copyright and heritage management.
7. National monitoring	The project contributes to support the implementation of Open Access in the fields of ADM and to include its research outputs in the monitoring system (i.e. institutional repositories).

Table 5. Contributions of the proposal to the action items of the OA Strategy

Provide examples of innovative components within your project, with respect to similar initiatives or projects. In particular, to what extent do you ensure the interoperability at national and international level?

The project is innovative by specifically addressing the needs of Swiss institutions and key stakeholders working in the disciplinary fields of ADM and by producing new tools to address the specific issues of these fields, which are relevant also for other disciplines (i.e. copyright management, open licenses, multimedia formats, reviewing processes for action-research and practice-based research). To guarantee interoperability at national and international level, it builds on existing national and international projects and initiatives, and it communicates its results and outputs to a broader selected network (please refer to the list of related initiatives in Table 6, annex to the proposal).

B) Impact, max. 5 pages

Describe your communication, promotion, standardisation and exploitation plan in order to guarantee the future positioning of the envisaged service at national and international level.

The communication plan is structured to address different targets with various communication tools. During 2022 and 2023 communication will focus on the project partners and stakeholders. In 2024 communication will involve publishers (international and national), and it will focus on disseminating the project results (see Table 7 and Table 8, below).

The project and all its content are released under the Creative Commons attribution license (CC BY 4.0); data are released under the Creative Commons zero license (CC0). Attribution is provided to the specific authors and the project (with a link to the project full credits).

For the status quo of the implementation of OA policies and people involved in the schools, see Table 9, annex to the proposal. A list of the requirements in terms of OS and OA coming from relevant grant-makers in the fields of ADM is available on Table 10, annex to the proposal. Requirements in term of OA from a selection of relevant publications in the field of ADM is available in Table 11, annex to the proposal.

Targets	Communication tools	Envisioned actions	Expected impact of the project /skills acquired
Swiss schools of art and design (see Table 9, annex) - swissuniversities members and partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Partnership agreement - Formal engagement in the project - Annual and final reports 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Swiss schools of art and design are expected to implement Open Access by 2024. Within the project they are asked to: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Support the project and be involved; 2. Define a local team; 3. Provide training and support measures within their institution. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Informed and involved - Feel supported and engaged
Local team (Open Access Officers, librarians, heads of research)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Meetings - Annual and final reports - Guidelines - Training organized by the project team - Coaching provided by the project team 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identifying relevant case studies and best practices (expected 20 in total) - Reviewing of the guidelines and reports - Participating in training - Training and coaching to researchers - 3 schools involved in the project organize workshops/seminars/courses related to Open Science for students - Relationships with 3 national specialised publishers in the field of ADM (publishing books in German, French and Italian) - Implementation of OA in institutional publications. - More broadly they need to support and coach researchers in their institutions, and they need technical and open science skills. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trained and supported - Skills gained: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training and communication skills to transmit and educate researchers and technicians on open science in the fields of ADM - Ability to communicate the guidelines and to coach in their use.

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Researchers and teachers of all Swiss schools of art and design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training and coaching organized by the local teams - Guidelines 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers are requested to publish in Green and Gold Open Access. Furthermore they are expected to produce FAIR and open data and to implement Open Science in different areas of their work (open software, open hardware, open review processes, citizen science). The need to use/reuse legally and properly content from other researchers and institutions (multimedia formats). The need to produce open research, practice-based research and new artworks/services/products. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness of Open Science - Feel engaged and supported - Access to guidelines and to Open Access Officers in their institution.
Students of all Swiss schools of art and design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training organized by the local teams (3 seminars/workshops/courses) - Guidelines 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use and reuse of images, texts, multimedia formats. - Production of images, texts, multimedia formats, new artworks/services/products. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness of Open Science - Awareness of copyright, open licenses, third parties copyright management
Institutional publications (see Table 9, annex)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct contacts and meetings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement Open Access to comply with the national Open Access strategy and implementation plan. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Green or Gold Open Access
National publishers (3 publishers specialised in ADM publishing books in Italian, French and German). See Table 11, annex	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct contacts and meetings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement Open Access to comply with the national Open Access strategy and implementation plan and the grant-makers requirements. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Green or Gold Open Access
International publishers (See Table 11, annex)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct contacts and meetings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open Access to comply with the international Open Access strategy and grant-makers requirements. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Green or Gold Open Access
Swiss networks in arts, design and music (SDN - Swiss Design Network, SARN - Swiss Artistic Research Network, CSUM – Conference of Swiss Universities of Music, Swiss Society of Musicology)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct contacts and meetings - Annual and final reports - Guidelines 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Endorsements - Review of the guidelines - Contributing in the project dissemination - Contributing in the follow up of the project - Implementation of Open Access in institutional conference proceeding and publications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support to the initiative - Better awareness of Open Science
Grant-makers (See Table 10, annex)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct contacts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support to Open Science and open Government data - Support access to data and results of publicly funded projects - Implementation of Open Access in institutional conference proceeding and publications 	
Existing networks and projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct contacts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possible use/reuse of content produced by the project guidelines and webinars 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Informed, use/reuse

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Other swissuniversities members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reports - Short description of the project published on swissuniversities website 	- Swiss schools of art and design are expected to implement Open Access by 2024.	- Informed
Swiss scientific community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contacts with existing networks and projects to provide the guidelines and the project outputs. 	- Possible use/reuse of content produced by the project guidelines and webinars	- Informed, use/reuse
International networks in the fields of arts, design and music (i.e. Dariah, International Federation of Theatre Research, International network for contemporary performing arts, European Music Council)			
Society (the project does not address directly society)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Indirect communication tools: License in journals and publications - Availability of journals and publications in open repositories - DOI on all publications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possibility to access and reuse research results, publications and data - Possibility to contribute to research and tools 	- (Indirect impact of the project)

Table 7. Communication targets, actions and expected impact.

Project outputs	Targets	Communication tools
Guidelines	- Open Access officers	Website (institutional website hosted by SUPSI or by another project partner; institutional websites assure their maintenance)
Webinars	- Researchers and students	

Table 8. Project outputs, targets and communication tools.

What are the expected benefits for the following target groups: swissuniversities members, their partners, the Swiss scientific community and the society?

The present project addresses the issue of managing third parties' assets in the frame of academic publications, which largely affects the disciplines of ADM. Arts and design scholar are often researching bodies of works of authors, artists, designers, whose images are protected by the copyright of the respective Estates or of public and private collections. Copyright owners can oppose to open access publications of such assets, thus limiting the effectiveness of research outputs and their dissemination. In the case of music and performing arts, the reproduction and/or re-enactment of works by living or deceased authors is subject to similar issues, and granting a solid legal framework for such body of works is often complex or inconclusive. Both cases offer insights into problematic topics that can be relevant for other disciplines: the respect of author's rights in the framework of OA can be relevant for scholars in the fields of literature and history,

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as well as for intellectual property managers. The DACS (UK's flagship visual artists' rights management organisation) is currently offering seminars open to researchers in order to address and answer their doubts concerning the management of visual assets. Thus, the present project can equally benefit GLAMs (galleries, libraries, archives and museums), that are including visual assets covered by copyright in their publications. See Table 12, below.

Target groups	Benefits
swissuniversities members	The project supports the swissuniversities 2021-2024 Open Access Strategy and Implementation Plan. It supports Open Science in Switzerland and more specifically it focuses on a selection of six swissuniversities members: SUPSI (with Accademia Di-mitri, Ticino), HES-SO (ECAL, Lausanne; HEAD – Genève; EDHEA, Valais), ZHdK (Zurich), HSLU Hochschule Luzern – Design & Kunst (Lucerne), BFH (Bern), FHNW (Basel).
Partners	The project supports the Digital Switzerland strategy with a focus on ADM (it also connects to Government data in the field of heritage, museums, archives, libraries and culture in general) and it involves stakeholders (national institutions working in the field of art and design, Swiss networks, Swiss grant-makers supporting culture and research in the fields of ADM...) with fall-outs in their work, in the reuse of their data and in access to scientific data.
Swiss scientific community	The project supports specifically the Swiss scientific community by providing 1. access to Green and Gold Open Access journals in the fields of art and design; 2. guidelines to deal with the process and to address common cases; 3. training. The project addresses specific issues in the disciplinary fields of ADM which are internationally relevant and which respond also to needs in other disciplinary fields (i.e. managing third parties rights, working with contemporary archives, managing rights of images, artworks and design).
Society	The project enlarges access to research results and data in the disciplinary fields of ADM. In particular by addressing issues of multimedia formats and by collaborating with stakeholders, it enriches the possibility for society to benefit from a wide variety of content.

Table 12. Expected benefits and target groups of the proposal

How does the project promote interdisciplinarity in order to produce effects outside its own field of applications?

The project extends its effects outside its scope of action by involving national networks and key stakeholders outside academia in the fields of art, design, music, heritage, culture, open license, legal studies, patents, art economy, librarianship and archiving (please refer to the lists of target groups, schools, grant-makers and journals, see Table 12, above and Table 11, annex to this proposal) and by collaborating with existing projects and networks in the field of Open Science (please refer to the list of related initiatives, Table 6, annex to this proposal).

To what extent will the proposed results and/or services strengthen the position of the Swiss scientific community at the international level?

The project addresses specific issues in the disciplinary fields of ADM which are internationally relevant, it produces guidelines released under an open license and it contributes to make journals and monographs in the field of art and design accessible in Green and Gold Open Access. Furthermore the project collaborates with existing projects and networks in the field of Open Access. In particular the partnership with DARIAH - The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities is specifically relevant to communicate

the project results at an international level and strengthen the role Switzerland has in this field.

How are you promoting gender and cultural diversity?

Gender and cultural diversity will be promoted within the project team and the local teams. Training provided will aim at responding to gender and cultural diversity.

How do the measures dealing with age diversity respond to the needs of researchers or pilot users at different stages of their career?

The tools produced by the project (guidelines, webinars and training implemented by the local teams) are meant to reach researchers at different stages of their career, as well as students.

If applicable, how does the project address the services usability (adaptation to different digital skills levels) and e-accessibility issues (adaptation to specific disabilities)?

The documentation published online will be developed following the web content accessibility guidelines (SUPSI has been involved in projects promoting accessibility to museums and heritage for people with impairments and disabilities since 2015). The open licenses also allow republishing research results, for example for text-to-speech readers.

What risks are you envisioning regarding the viability of the project once the funding from the OS programme stops? How are you going to address these risks concretely?

To guarantee the viability of the project once the funding from the OS programme stops, the project is structured into centralised and local services. The centralised service is developed by the project team in 2022-2024 to provide support, training, guidelines and networking to local teams; the local teams will continue to operate after the end of the project. Eventually specific centralised activities could be activated after 2024 by consultants (i.e. update of the guidelines, new case studies); we are discussing the potential role of SARN Swiss Artistic Research Network to collect feedback and eventually to lead the follow up of the project

C) Mobilization of Resources, max. 10 pages

Describe the structure of the project (e.g. PERT diagram). Please explain how this project structure seems to respond optimally to the objectives you have set.

See Table 13, below.

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Activities	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Coordination and communication	- Project design - Definition of the local teams	- Start-up of the project (meeting), interim report	- Annual report (Jan 2023), interim report - 2 meetings	- Annual report (Jan 2024), interim report - 2 meetings - Final report (Dec 2024)	- Follow up Activities
Guidelines		- Documentation about research practices in the field of ADM - Identifying relevant case studies and best practices (expected 20) - Analysis of a selection of case studies produce with the support of legal advice (selection of 10 case studies) - Production of guidelines - Reviewing of the guidelines - Editing and publication of the guidelines			
Training			- Production of 3 webinars - Training and coaching to trainers - Training and coaching to researchers - 3 schools involved in the project organize workshops/seminars/courses related to Open Science for their students.		

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National publishers				- Relationships with 3 national specialised publishers in the field of ADM - Implementation of OA on institutional publications (70%)	
International publishers				- Documentation about practices of publishers specialised in ADM in the field of Open Access - Networking with international publishers in the field of ADM to support 5 in Open Access - Relationships with DOAJ	
Communication and dissemination	- Direct contact - Involvement of partners and stakeholders - Informing networks about the project		- Institutional website with guidelines, recorded webinars and other documents (June 2023)	- Public presentation of the project results with invitation to journals and publishers (May-June 2024) - Public presentation of the project results and publishers involved (Oct 2024) - Communication and dissemination of the project guidelines and tools at a national and international level, within the institution and among researchers and students	- Maintenance of the website - Collecting requests for a review of the guidelines

Table 13. Structure of the project

Description of the work packages. Only one work package is imposed, it is the coordination of the project (including management, communication and dissemination of results). Partner no 1 is by default the person in charge of this work package.

Work package table					
No	Title	Responsible Partner	Effort (PM ²)	Start (Month)	End(Month)
1	Coordination and dissemination (Table 15, below)	SUPSI	38.90	M1 Jan 2022	M36 Dec 2024
2	Guidelines (Table 16, below)	Project team	27.74	M1 Jan 2022	M12 Dec 2022
3	Training (Table 17, below)	Project team with local teams	8.02	M13 Jan 2023	M24 Dec 2023
4	Publications (Table 18, below)	Project team with local teams	5.17	M25 Jan 2024	M36 Dec 2024

Table 14. Work packages

Work package no	1	Work package title				Coordination		
Responsible partner		1 : SUPSI						
Partner number		1	2	3	4	5	6	Total
		SUPSI	FHNW	HES-SO	HKB	HSLU	ZHdK	
Effort per partner (PM)		17.42	3.87	3.87	3.87	2.13	3.87	38.9
Month of start		Jan 22				Month of end		Dec 24
Objectives: Coordination, organization, project management, communication and dissemination								
Description of the tasks and roles of the partners for each of them								
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of the local teams - Partners 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 • Definition of the calendar of webinars and trainings for 2023 and the formats (identified periods March-April 2023, October 2023) - Project team and local teams • Administrative management of the project - Project team coordinated by partner 1 • Communication with program coordination - Project team coordinated by partner 1 • Communication within the project - Project team coordinated by partner 1 • Quality control and risk Management - Project team coordinated by partner 1 • Communication and dissemination of the project guidelines and tools at a national and international level to target publics - Project team coordinated by partner 1 • Public Relations - Project team coordinated by partner 1 • Communication and dissemination of the project guidelines and tools within the institution and among researchers and students - Local teams of partners 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 • Active involvement of the Swiss schools of art and design - Project team coordinated by partner 1 • Review of the reports - Local teams of partners 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 • Participation in the meetings - Local teams of partners 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 								
Milestones								
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kick-off meeting (Jan-Feb 2022) • Meetings (May-June 2022, Nov-Dec 2022, May-June 2023, Nov-Dec 2023, May-June 2024, Nov-Dec 2024) 								
List of deliverables (month)								
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project contract (Jan 2022) D1 • List of local teams (Jan 2022) D2 • Annual reports (Jan 2023, Jan 2024) D3a, D3b • Interim Report (June 2022, June 2023, June 2024) D4a, D4b, D4c • Business model for the service emanating from the project • Public presentation of the project results (May-June 2024) D5 • Institutional website with guidelines, recorded webinars and documents (June 2023) D6 • Final Report (Dec 2024) D7 • Service Description (Dec 2024) • Summary of results (Dec 2024) 								

Table 15. Structure of WP1

² PM means person-month, the unit of measurement for work.

Work package no	2	Work package title					Coordination	
Responsible partner	1 : SUPSI with the project team and the local teams							
Partner number	1	2	3	4	5	6	Total	
	SUPSI	FHNW	HES-SO	HKB	HSLU	ZHdK		
Effort per partner (PM)	21.42	1.16	1.16	1.16	0.52	1.16	27.74	
Month of start	Jan 22	Month of end				Dec 22		
Objectives: Production of the project guidelines to support the implementation of Open Access in the fields of art and design								
Description of the tasks and roles of the partners for each of them								
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Documenting research practices in the field of ADM - Project team coordinated by partner 1 Identifying relevant case studies and best practices (expected 20) - Local teams of partners 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 Analysis of a selection of case studies produce with the support of legal advice (selection of 10 case studies) - Project team coordinated by partner 1 Production of guidelines - Project team coordinated by partner 1 Reviewing of the guidelines - Local teams of partners 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 Editing and publication of the guidelines - Project team coordinated by partner 1 								
List of deliverables (month)								
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> List of relevant case studies and best practices (Feb-March 2022) D8 Selection of relevant case studies (March-April 2022) D9 Structure of the guidelines (April 2022) D10 Draft of the guidelines (September 2022) D11 Publication of the guidelines (Dec 2022) D12 								

Table 16. Structure of WP2

Work package no	3	Work package title					Coordination	
Responsible partner	1 : SUPSI with the project team and the local teams							
Partner number	1	2	3	4	5	6	Total	
	SUPSI	FHNW	HES-SO	HKB	HSLU	ZHdK		
Effort per partner (PM)	0.15	1.42	1.42	1.42	0.77	1.42	8.02	
Month of start	Jan 23	Month of end				Dec 23		
Objectives: Production of the project guidelines to support the implementation of Open Access in the fields of art and design								
Description of the tasks and roles of the partners for each of them								
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Production of 3 webinars - Project team coordinated by partner 1 Training and coaching to trainers - Project team coordinated by partner 1 Participating in training - Local teams of partners 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 Training and coaching to researchers - Local teams of partners 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 3 schools involved in the project organize workshops/seminars/courses related to Open Science for their students - Local teams of partners 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 (TBD) 								
List of deliverables (month)								
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3 webinars (March-April 2023, October 2023) D13a, D13b, D13c 6 trainings for researchers (March-April 2023, October 2023) D14a, D14b, D14c 3 schools involved in the project organize workshops/seminars/courses related to Open Science for their students (March-April 2023, October 2023) D15a, D15b, D15c 								

Table 17. Structure of WP3

Work package no	4	Work package title					Coordination	
Responsible partner	1 : SUPSI with the project team and the local teams							
Partner number	1	2	3	4	5	6	Total	
	SUPSI	FHNW	HES-SO	HKB	HSLU	ZHdK		
Effort per partner (PM)	0.13	0.84	0.84	0.84	0.84	0.84	5.17	
Month of start	Jan 24	Month of end				Dec 24		
Objectives: Negotiations to with international, national and institutional publisher								
Description of the tasks and roles of the partners for each of them								
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Documentation about practices of publishers specialised in ADM in the field of Open Access - Project team coordinated by partner 1 								

- Networking with international publishers in the field of ADM to support 5 in Open Access - Project team coordinated by partner 1
- Relationships with DOAJ - Project team coordinated by partner 1
- Suggesting publishers and publications (Partner 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6)
- Relationships with 3 national specialised publishers in the field of ADM - Local teams of three partners (TBD)
- Implementation of OA on institutional publications (70%) - Local teams of partners 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6
- Support and coaching - Project team coordinated by partner 1

List of deliverables (month)

- 70% of institutional publications in Green or Gold Open Access (June 2024) D16
- 3 international journals in Green or Gold Open Access (June 2024) D17
- 3 national publishers in Green or Gold Open Access options (June 2024) D18

Table 18. Structure of WP4

Describe the work plan (graphical articulation of work packages and tasks and key deliverables over time).

Quarters	2022				2023				2024			
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
WP1	D1 D2	D4a			D3a	D4b D6			D3b	D4c D5		D7
WP2	D8	D9 D10	D11	D12								
WP3					D13a D14a D15a	D13b D14b D15b		D13c D14c D15c				
WP4										D16 D17 D18		

Please complete the milestone table: This table includes 2 to 3 milestones imposed by the program, and can be completed with the project's own milestones. An interim evaluation milestone is only required for projects lasting 24 months or more.

Milestones	
Date (Month)	Milestone
Jan-Feb 2022	Project Kick-off meeting
May-June 2022	Project meeting and Interim evaluation
October 2022	Open Access week - Review of the guidelines closes
Nov-Dec 2022	Project meeting and annual evaluation
May-June 2023	Project meeting and Interim evaluation
October 2023	Open Access week - Session of trainings and webinars
Nov-Dec 2023	Project meeting and annual evaluation
May-June 2024	Project meeting and Interim evaluation
	Public presentation of the project results with invitation to journals and publishers (May-June 2024)
October 2024	Open Access week public presentation of the project and of the journals and publication in Green and Gold Open Access
Nov-Dec 2024	Project meeting - final evaluation

Table 19. Milestones of the project

Please complete the table of deliverables. This table includes mandatory deliverables. Other deliverables may be inserted by the consortium. Three statuses are possible: public (accessible and distributed in open access), restricted (accessible by the experts appointed for the follow-up of the project and the members of the Open Science Delegation), and internal (only accessible to the project partners themselves).

Date	Deliverable Title	Status
Jan 2022	Project contract between swissuniversities and the leading house SUPSI (Jan 2022)	Restricted
	List of local teams (Jan 2022)	Public
Feb-March 2022	List of relevant case studies and best practices (Feb-March 2022)	Public
March-April 2022	Selection of relevant case studies (March-April 2022)	Public
April 2022	Structure of the guidelines (April 2022)	Public
June 2022	Interim Report (June 2022, June 2023, June 2024)	Public
Sep 2022	Draft of the guidelines (September 2022)	Public
Dec 2022	Publication of the guidelines (Dec 2022)	Public
Jan 2023	Annual report	Public
March-April 2023, Oct 2023	1-2 webinars (March-April 2023, October 2023)	Public
	6 trainings for researchers (March-April 2023, October 2023)	Open to researchers
	3 schools involved in the project organize workshops/seminars/courses related to Open Science for their students (March-April 2023, October 2023)	Open to students
June 2023	Institutional website with guidelines, recorded webinars and other documents (June 2023)	Public
	Interim Report (June 2022, June 2023, June 2024)	Public
Oct 2023	Training and Open Access week	Public
Jan 2024	Annual report (Jan 2023, Jan 2024)	Public
May-June 2024	Public presentation of the project results with invitation to journals and publishers (May-June 2024)	Public
June 2024	Interim Report (June 2022, June 2023, June 2024)	Public
Dec 2024	Business model for the service(s) emanating from the project	Public
	Final report	Public
	Service Description	Public
	Summary of results	Public

Table 20. Deliverables

Please complete the risk management table. The table includes an imposed risk regarding the sustainability of services (for projects that provide such service(s)).

Title of Risk	Description	Possible mitigation	Probable consequence	Level
Outdated guidelines	The guidelines provide procedures which take into account current legislations, tools and infrastructures	Involvement of the Swiss networks for art and design for the follow up of the project and to collect the possible need for a revision of the guidelines	The guidelines are obsolete and do not respond to existing tools and legislation.	Medium
Poor quality of the guidelines	The guidelines do not respond to the needed of researchers and of the institutions involved	Identification of a series of case studies connected to the institutions involved (relevance); involvement of a specialised project team open to consultants; review process of the guidelines; one year to produce and process the guidelines	Low relevance of the project results	Medium
Webinars in English	Webinars are produced in English with difficulties in sharing them with students and some scholars.	Possibility of producing webinars in German, French and Italian, curated by the local teams with the support of the project team	Need for other webinars and training	Low
Impossibility of releasing a selection of content in Open Access (third parties content, artworks)	Scientific publications including images from third parties or artwork can not be published in Open Access or need to be published without images.	Addressing directly this issue within the project; possibility to include in the guidelines innovative solutions such as multimedia institutional websites; brainstorming with local teams, research teams and stakeholders; possibility to involve stakeholders (i.e. swissuniversities, grant makers, international networks) for an endorsement of the working direction proposed within the project	Limited application of Open Access to the fields of ADM; necessity to endorse alternative forms of publication	High
Heterogeneity of research outputs in the fields of art and design	Difficulty in defining scientific research and papers in the fields of art and design with relevant documentation which is not in the form of paper (i.e. multimedia formats, catalogues, exhibitions, prototypes, workshops, action-research and practice-based research...)			
Limited use of the guidelines and webinars created by the project	The guidelines and the webinars produced by the project are accessed by few people	Communication and dissemination activities for one year; direct contact with stakeholders; use of the communication channels of the institutions involved; involvement of national networks	Low relevance of the project results	Medium

swissuniversities

Inefficient training for trainers	Training does not provide sufficient support for local teams who will have to implement training in their institutions	Collaboration with existing networks and initiatives supporting Open Science training; one year to focus on training and coaching; production of webinars, specific trainings and one-to-one coaching	Need for other webinars and training	Medium
Homogeneity of the participants in the training	The participants involved in training are not gender balanced (with a predominance of women) and they do not include diversity	The training is open; it is communicated through networks, stakeholders and the institutions involved; it is accessible through different formats (online, in-person, through the guidelines); online documentation is released with open licenses and it is published using the digital accessibility guidelines; specific participants are triggered	Limited gender balance and diversity within the project	Medium
Reluctance of publishers	Impossibility to find an agreement with publishers for Green or Gold Open Access	Initiating contacts with publishers in 2021; collaborating with publishers already known by the institutions; use of national and international studies about impact of OA for monographs; collaboration with Grantmakers in the negotiation process; collaboration with other publishers; possible collaboration with CSAL Consortium of Swiss Academic Libraries	Limited number of Open Access publishers and journals in the fields of art and design	High
Reluctance of scholars in the fields of art and design	Difficulty in convincing scholars in the fields of ADM of the importance of Open Science. Unwillingness to open content for commercial use. Fear of opening content and someone will use it for commercial purposes. Feeling of a lack of evaluation and reputation mechanisms in their fields considering Open Access; limited number of publicly funded research in the fields of ADM	Using content and arguments supporting Open Science from other initiatives; creating a space for brainstorming and discussion that allow to reflect on the advantages of Open Science in the fields of art and design (i.e. open culture, collaboration with GLAMs, reuse of content from cultural institutions/archives also for design, fashion and new art works, increased visibility of research outputs, collaboration with open online collaborative projects such as Wikipedia, Wikidata, Wikimedia Commons); focusing on content produced within research financed by SNF and Europe (explicit requirements of Grantmakers); application of institutional Open Access and Open Science policies	Limited Open Access in the fields of ADM	High

Sustainability	The centralised service is guaranteed during the project (2022-2024). After the end of the project the local services are maintained by the local teams.	The project is well-connected to the 2024 timeframe for Open Access in Switzerland; the structure of the project is meant to support local teams to continue the activities after the end of the project; limited costs for a follow-up of the project (i.e. review and update of the guidelines)	The program does not include this service in its service portfolio.	Medium
Maintenance of the project website	The documentation of the project needs to be made available on an Internet website after the end of the project	The website is created as an institutional website to guarantee its regular maintenance; collaboration of existing networks; documentation published also on Zenodo and eventually GitHub. Backup of the Internet Archive	The website is available online on the Internet Archive	Medium
Limited involvement of the Swiss schools of art and design	The Swiss schools of art and design are not actively involved in the project	Clear identification of their role and of the activities of the local teams; fundings provided by the institutions for their local teams and activities; regular meetings	Limited use of the project results and limited pertinence of the project	Medium

Table 21. Risk management

Effectiveness Questions:

What indicators and verification measures are you proposing for the evaluability of project activities?

- Structure of the guidelines including 1. practices in the fields of ADM from all the partners involved, 2. practices of publishers in these fields and 3. responses to major issues related to the implementation of Open Access in the fields of ADM.
- Feedback related to the guidelines: the feedback is requested from the local teams and the stakeholders involved (review process) - criteria: the guidelines present relevant case studies, they provide answers/solutions and relevant information/indications.
- Publication of the guidelines or reuse of content from the guidelines by partners and stakeholders.
- Implementation of the training: involvement of participants from all local teams/partner institutions, balanced number of participants male and female, feedback related to the training sessions, capacity of the local teams to implement training in their institutions, pertinence of the training in the partners institutions for students and scholars.
- Green or Gold Open Access implemented on institutional publications (expected 70% of the current institutional publications).
- Green or Gold Open Access implemented by international and national publishers (expected three international publishers and three national publishers).
- Institutional website with the documentation of the project and/or agreement with a stakeholder for the follow up of the project.

How is the risk management matrix evaluable?

The risk assessment was created by identifying risks for each activity planned within the project. The evaluation of the risks drove to a mitigation plan which was included within the project. The evaluation reported in the risk management table considers likelihood, probability and impact (see Table 21, above).

How does the adopted work plan support the achievement of project objectives?

The work plan is designed to support Swiss schools of art and design in implementing Open Access by 2024 and to achieve all the specific project objectives in line with the national Open Access strategy and implementation plan (see Table 22, annex to this proposal, and Table 23, annex to this proposal).

How does the governance of your project safeguard the proper participation of partners and clients/users in the decision-making?

The structure of the project combines a centralised approach and a decentralised approach. The governance of the project is assured by the centralised team which involves all partners in regular meetings – twice a year – to inform, collect feedback and engage all project members in the decision-making process. The support provided by the centralised service and implemented by the project team is based on the case studies proposed by the local teams; guidelines and reports are reviewed by the local teams. Training and coaching is provided on-demand and by working in small working groups. The project proposal was reviewed by all partners involved and adjusted according to feedback and proposals to better suit the needs of each school.

Efficiency Questions:

To what extent is your project avoiding duplication of effort and redundancy among swissuniversities members?

By involving all Swiss schools of art and design and their Open Access officers (i.e. in the cases of HES-SO, ZHdK and SUPSI), the project avoids duplication of effort and redundancy among swissuniversities members in the fields of ADM. Furthermore it ensures to benefit from existing tools and experiences by collaborating with existing projects and networks.

To what extent does your project team have the necessary skills to achieve the objectives?

The project team is managed by Iolanda Pensa and led by Iolanda Pensa and Davide Fornari. It further includes a scientific collaborator and a legal consultancy.

How could the available resources be improved or optimized (or even completed during project implementation) to achieve the objectives?

Within the project structure, funding and in-kind contributions from the partners are essentially meant to support the local teams and their activities; while the federal contribution is meant to support the centralised service implemented by the project team. This distribution of resources and expenses allows the Swiss schools of art and design to commit and invest resources into the local implementation of the OA Strategy and Action Plan within their institution, while benefiting from the support of the project. The project starts in 2022 to allow all partners to allocate the necessary resources in their financial plans.

Project Budget

Please select one of the Excel forms and attach it to your application.

Forms available :

- Budget Form PgB_Individual Project or
- Budget Form PgB_Multiple Projects

Federal contribution

Project funds must be used by the end date of the project. An extension of the project may be granted by the program coordination, up to the end of December 2024, without modification of the federal contribution granted. In this case, the unused balance must be returned to SERI.

Own contribution

Own contributions may take the form of financial and in-kind contributions. Up to the amount allocated by the federal contribution, 50% of the own contribution must be provided in the form of real money. In other words, the own contribution in real money must be at least 50% of the federal contribution.

Real money contributions refer to the financing of costs incurred by the participation in the project in addition to the ordinary current expenses. These include :

- Personnel costs, including social security charges
- Material costs such as devices and equipment, operating resources already in place, rental of premises specifically allocated to the project, costs for conferences and travel

In-kind contributions (virtual money) refer to existing personnel resources, equipment and devices as well as operating resources already in place insofar as they are clearly earmarked and accounted for in the project. The services provided by employees funded by a national subsidy program (e.g. SNSF) are considered to be in-kind contributions.

Remarks

Annexes to the present application

Budget Form PgB Multiple Projects

Detailed budget

Table 2. Areas and activities

Table 6. Related initiatives

Table 9. Local team and activities

Table 10. OS and OA requirements of relevant grant-makers in the field of ADM

Table 11. OA requirements of a selection of relevant publications in the field of ADM

Table 22. Specific project objectives, activities and deliverables

Table 23. Problems and envisioned topics for the guidelines

Profiles of the team members

Letter of support from DARIAH

Letter of support from Pro Helvetia Swiss Arts Council

Letter of support from Swiss Federal Office of Culture

Letter of support from Swiss Artistic Research Network

Letter of support from Swiss Design Network

Letter of acknowledgement from Swiss National Science Foundation

3. Signatures Page

Project Acronym : OS-ADM

Signature of the project management

Mendrisio, May 28, 2021:

Signature of the project management (Dr. Iolanda Pensa)

Signature(s) of the rector, president or director of the Higher Education Institution(s)

Manno, May 28, 2021:

Franco Gervasoni, Director

Signature leading house 1,
SUPSI – Scuola universitaria professionale della Svizzera italiana

Basel, May 28, 2021:

Signature of the partner institution 2,
FHNW – Fachhochschule Nordwestschweiz

Delémont, May 28, 2021:

Signature of the partner institution 3,
HES-SO – Haute Ecole Spécialisée de Suisse occidentale

Bern, May 28, 2021:

Signature of the partner institution 4,
HKB – Hochschule der Künste Bern

Luzern, May 28, 2021:

Signature of the partner institution 5:
HSLU Hochschule Luzern – Design & Kunst

Zürich, May 28, 2021:

Signature of the partner institution 6:
ZHdK – Zürcher Hochschule der Künste

3. Signatures Page

Project Acronym : OS-ADM

Signature of the project management

Mendrisio, May 28, 2021:

Signature of the project management (Dr. Iolanda Pensa)

Signature(s) of the rector, president or director of the Higher Education Institution(s)

Manno, May 28, 2021:

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Basel, May 28, 2021:

Crispino Bergamaschi, President of the Board of Directors

Signature of the partner institution 2,
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Delémont, May 28, 2021:

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Bern, May 28, 2021:

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Luzern, May 28, 2021:

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Zürich, May 28, 2021:

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3. Signatures Page

Project Acronym : OS-ADM

Signature of the project management

Mendrisio, May 28, 2021:

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Luciana Vaccaro, Rector

Bern, May 28, 2021:

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Luzern, May 28, 2021:

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Zürich, May 28, 2021:

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ZHdK – Zürcher Hochschule der Künste

3. Signatures Page

Project Acronym : OS-ADM

Signature of the project management

Mendrisio, May 28, 2021:

Signature of the project management (Dr. Iolanda Pensa)

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Manno, May 28, 2021:

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Bern, May 28, 2021:

Thomas Beck, Director

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3. Signatures Page

Project Acronym : OS-ADM

Signature of the project management

Mendrisio, May 28, 2021:

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Gabriela Christen, Director

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Zürich, May 28, 2021:

Signature of the partner institution 6:
ZHdK – Zürcher Hochschule der Künste

3. Signatures Page

Project Acronym : OS-ADM

Signature of the project management

Mendrisio, May 28, 2021:

Signature of the project management (Dr. Iolanda Pensa)

Signature(s) of the rector, president or director of the Higher Education Institution(s)

Manno, May 28, 2021:

Signature leading house 1,
SUPSI – Scuola universitaria professionale della Svizzera italiana

Basel, May 28, 2021:

Signature of the partner institution 2,
FHNW – Fachhochschule Nordwestschweiz

Delémont, May 28, 2021:

Signature of the partner institution 3,
HES-SO – Haute Ecole Spécialisée de Suisse occidentale

Bern, May 28, 2021:

Signature of the partner institution 4,
HKB – Hochschule der Künste Bern

Luzern, May 28, 2021:

Signature of the partner institution 5:
HSLU Hochschule Luzern – Design & Kunst

Zürich, May 28, 2021:

Thomas D. Meier, Director

Signature of the partner institution 6:
ZHdK – Zürcher Hochschule der Künste

2021	Federal Contribution ¹	Own contributions of HEIs and institutions in the field of HEIS entitled to contributions ²			Other contributions of project partners without entitlement to funding ³	Budget total
		Real Money ⁴	Virtual Money	Total own contributions		
in CHF only the fields marked in yellow	Fill in					
SUPSI Scuola universitaria professionale della Svizzera italiana						
Personnel costs	0	0	0	0	0	0
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	0	0	0	0	0	0
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
FHNW Fachhochschule Nordwestschweiz						
Personnel costs	0	0	0	0	0	0
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	0	0	0	0	0	0
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
HES-SO Haute École Spécialisée de Suisse occidentale						
Personnel costs	0	0	0	0	0	0
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	0	0	0	0	0	0
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
HKB Hochschule der Künste Bern						
Personnel costs	0	0	0	0	0	0
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	0	0	0	0	0	0
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
HSLU Hochschule Luzern Design & Kunst						
Personnel costs	0	0	0	0	0	0
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	0	0	0	0	0	0
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
ZHdK Zürcher Hochschule der Künste						
Personnel costs	0	0	0	0	0	0
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	0	0	0	0	0	0
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
Project Total						
Personnel costs	0	0	0	0	0	0
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	0	0	0	0	0
Final total	0	0	0	0	0	0
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		

2022	Federal Contribution ¹	Own contributions of HEIs and institutions in the field of HEIS entitled to contributions ²			Other contributions of project partners without entitlement to funding ³	Budget total
		Real Money ⁴	Virtual Money	Total own contributions		
in CHF only the fields marked in yellow	Fill in					
SUPSI Scuola universitaria professionale della Svizzera italiana						
Personnel costs	175027	19000	6000	25000	0	200027
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	1500	1000	0	1000	0	2500
Total	176'527	20'000	6'000	26'000	0	202'527
Real-Money part and own contributions		11.3%		14.7%		
FHNW Fachhochschule Nordwestschweiz						
Personnel costs	0	19000	6000	25000	0	25000
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	1000	0	1000	0	1000
Total	0	20'000	6'000	26'000	0	26'000
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
HES-SO Haute École Spécialisée de Suisse occidentale						
Personnel costs	0	19000	6000	25000	0	25000
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	1000	0	1000	0	1000
Total	0	20'000	6'000	26'000	0	26'000
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
HKB Hochschule der Künste Bern						
Personnel costs	0	19000	6000	25000	0	25000
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	1000	0	1000	0	1000
Total	0	20'000	6'000	26'000	0	26'000
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
HSLU Hochschule Luzern Design & Kunst						
Personnel costs	0	9000	6000	15000	0	15000
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	1000	0	1000	0	1000
Total	0	10'000	6'000	16'000	0	16'000
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
ZHdK Zürcher Hochschule der Künste						
Personnel costs	0	19000	6000	25000	0	25000
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	1000	0	1000	0	1000
Total	0	20'000	6'000	26'000	0	26'000
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
Project Total						
Personnel costs	175027	104000	36000	140000	0	315027
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	1500	6000	0	6000	0	7500
Final total	176527	110000	36000	146000	0	322527
Real-Money part and own contributions		62.3%		82.7%		

2023	Federal Contribution ¹	Own contributions of HEIs and institutions in the field of HEIS entitled to contributions ²			Other contributions of project partners without entitlement to funding ³	Budget total
in CHF only the fields marked in yellow	Fill in	Real Money ⁴	Virtual Money	Total own contributions		
SUPSI Scuola universitaria professionale della Svizzera italiana						
Personnel costs	59367	18500	7000	25500	0	84867
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	1000	1500	0	1500	0	2500
Total	60'367	20'000	7'000	27'000	0	87'367
Real-Money part and own contributions		33.1%		44.7%		
FHNW Fachhochschule Nordwestschweiz						
Personnel costs	0	18500	7000	25500	0	25500
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	1500	0	1500	0	1500
Total	0	20'000	7'000	27'000	0	27'000
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
HES-SO Haute École Spécialisée de Suisse occidentale						
Personnel costs	0	18500	7000	25500	0	25500
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	1500	0	1500	0	1500
Total	0	20'000	7'000	27'000	0	27'000
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
HKB Hochschule der Künste Bern						
Personnel costs	0	18500	7000	25500	0	25500
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	1500	0	1500	0	1500
Total	0	20'000	7'000	27'000	0	27'000
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
HSLU Hochschule Luzern Design & Kunst						
Personnel costs	0	9000	7000	16000	0	16000
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	1000	0	1000	0	1000
Total	0	10'000	7'000	17'000	0	17'000
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
ZHdK Zürcher Hochschule der Künste						
Personnel costs	0	18500	7000	25500	0	25500
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	1500	0	1500	0	1500
Total	0	20'000	7'000	27'000	0	27'000
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
Project Total						
Personnel costs	59367	101500	42000	143500	0	202867
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	1000	8500	0	8500	0	9500
Final total	60367	110000	42000	152000	0	212367
Real-Money part and own contributions		182.2%		251.8%		

2024	Federal Contribution ¹	Own contributions of HEIs and institutions in the field of HEIS entitled to contributions ²			Other contributions of project partners without entitlement to funding ³	Budget total
in CHF only the fields marked in yellow	Fill in	Real Money ⁴	Virtual Money	Total own contributions		
SUPSI Scuola universitaria professionale della Svizzera italiana						
Personnel costs	110566	14000	7000	21000	0	131566
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	1000	6000	0	6000	0	7000
Total	111'566	20'000	7'000	27'000	0	138'566
Real-Money part and own contributions		17.9%		24.2%		
FHNW Fachhochschule Nordwestschweiz						
Personnel costs	0	14000	7000	21000	0	21000
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	6000	0	6000	0	6000
Total	0	20'000	7'000	27'000	0	27'000
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
HES-SO Haute École Spécialisée de Suisse occidentale						
Personnel costs	0	14000	7000	21000	0	21000
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	6000	0	6000	0	6000
Total	0	20'000	7'000	27'000	0	27'000
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
HKB Hochschule der Künste Bern						
Personnel costs	0	14000	7000	21000	0	21000
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	6000	0	6000	0	6000
Total	0	20'000	7'000	27'000	0	27'000
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
HSLU Hochschule Luzern Design & Kunst						
Personnel costs	0	4000	7000	11000	0	11000
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	6000	0	6000	0	6000
Total	0	10'000	7'000	17'000	0	17'000
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
ZHdK Zürcher Hochschule der Künste						
Personnel costs	0	14000	7000	21000	0	21000
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	6000	0	6000	0	6000
Total	0	20'000	7'000	27'000	0	27'000
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
Project Total						
Personnel costs	110566	74000	42000	116000	0	226566
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	1000	36000	0	36000	0	37000
Final total	111566	110000	42000	152000	0	263566
Real-Money part and own contributions		98.6%		136.2%		

2021-2024	Federal Contribution ¹	Own contributions of HEIs and institutions in the field of HEIS entitled to contributions ²			Other contributions of project partners without entitlement to funding ³	Budget total
		Real Money ⁴	Virtual Money	Total own contributions		
in CHF only the fields marked in yellow	Fill in					
SUPSI Scuola universitaria professionale della Svizzera italiana						
Personnel costs	344960	51500	20000	71500	0	416460
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	3500	8500	0	8500	0	12000
Total	348'460	60'000	20'000	80'000	0	428'460
Real-Money part and own contributions		17.2%		23.0%		
FHNW Fachhochschule Nordwestschweiz						
Personnel costs	0	51500	20000	71500	0	71500
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	8500	0	8500	0	8500
Total	0	60'000	20'000	80'000	0	80'000
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
HES-SO Haute École Spécialisée de Suisse occidentale						
Personnel costs	0	51500	20000	71500	0	71500
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	8500	0	8500	0	8500
Total	0	60'000	20'000	80'000	0	80'000
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
HKB Hochschule der Künste Bern						
Personnel costs	0	51500	20000	71500	0	71500
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	8500	0	8500	0	8500
Total	0	60'000	20'000	80'000	0	80'000
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
HSLU Hochschule Luzern Design & Kunst						
Personnel costs	0	22000	20000	42000	0	42000
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	8000	0	8000	0	8000
Total	0	30'000	20'000	50'000	0	50'000
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
ZHdK Zürcher Hochschule der Künste						
Personnel costs	0	51500	20000	71500	0	71500
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	0	8500	0	8500	0	8500
Total	0	60'000	20'000	80'000	0	80'000
Real-Money part and own contributions		#DIV/0!		#DIV/0!		
Project Total						
Personnel costs	344960	279500	120000	399500	0	744460
Material costs for devices and equipment	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other material costs	3500	50500	0	50500	0	54000
Final total	348460	330000	120000	450000	0	798460
Real-Money part and own contributions		94.7%		129.1%		

Centralized activities										Costs per year						
Work Package	Description	Who	Units	Days	Total cost	Cost per hour	Total hours	Consultants	Editor	Senior	Senior	Travel	2022	2023	2024 Total	
CC/Judicial law	Legal consultant	CC/Judicial law			60000	60000	50	60000					20000	20000	20000	
Guidelines	Legal advice	Lawyer	10	1	20000	250	80	20000					12000	40000	4000	
Guidelines	Preparing the documentation	Expert	2	15	19200	80	240			11520		7680	19200		20000	
Guidelines	Preparing the documentation	Consultant	2	6	7680	80	96	7680					7680		19200	
Guidelines	Documentation of case studies	Editor	20	2	25600	50	512		25600				25600		25600	
Guidelines	Guidelines based on the case studies and the lawyer	Editor	2	2	25600	50	512		25600				25600		25600	
Guidelines	Review	Expert	2	10	12800	80	160		16000		6400		12800		12800	
Guidelines	Specialised contributions and reviews	Consultants	5	5	16000	80	200		16000				16000		16000	
Guidelines	Publication editing	Editor	1	10	6400	50	128		6400				6400		6400	
Guidelines	Website content	Editor	1	10	6400	50	128		6400				6400		6400	
Guidelines	Graphic design	Expert	1	7	4480	80	56		4480		4480				4480	
Training	Coaching	Consultants	5	1	3200	80	40	3200						3200	3200	
Training	Webinars e training materials	Consultants	3	1	1920	80	24		1920					1920	1920	
Training	Webinars e training materials	Expert	2	1	1280	80	16		1280		640			1280	1280	
Training	Preparatory work	Editor	3	5	9600	50	192		9600					9600	9600	
International publishers	Preparatory work	Editor	1	20	12800	50	256		12800		3200				12800	
International publishers	Preparatory work, Best practices and alternative forms of publication	Expert	1	5	3200	80	40		3200						3200	
International publishers	Relationships with DOJ	Expert	5	1	3200	80	40		3200		960				3200	
International publishers	Contacts with publishers	Expert	5	1	3200	80	40		3200		960				3200	
National publishers	Support for the relationships with the national publishers and the institutional publications/research outputs	Expert	10	1	6400	80	80		6400		1920				6400	
Dissemination	Communication with the stakeholders, information about the project, project updates	Editor	1	40	25600	50	512		25600						25600	
Dissemination	Meetings, presentation of the results, contacts with stakeholders	Expert	2	10	12800	80	160		12800		7680				12800	
Coordination	Overview of the project, problem-solving, networking, meetings	Expert	3	10	19200	80	240		19200		19200				19200	
Documentation	Meetings, travels, materials	Editor	1	60	38400	50	768		38400						38400	
Expenses			CHF500	7	CHF3500		5720		CHF3500				12800	12800	CHF3500	
			224		CHF348460		5720	CHF108300	CHF150400	CHF52480	CHF33280	CHF3500	CHF1167	CHF1167	CHF3500	
							Per year	CHF36267	CHF50133	CHF17493	CHF11093	CHF1167	Total check	CHF348460	CHF11567	CHF348460

Activities for each partner Budget 80'000 chf

Work package	Description	Number of	Units	Days	Total cost	Cost per hour	Total hours	Costs per year		
								2022	2023	2024
Guidelines	Selection of case	3	3	1	5'760	80	72	5'760		
Guidelines	Review of the	3	3	1	5'760	80	72	5'760		
Training	Participating in	3	3	1	5'760	80	72		5'760	
Training	Training for	2	2	1	2'560	80	32		2'560	
Training	Training for	3	3	1	5'760	80	72		5'760	
Local publishers	Relationships	1	3	1	1'920	80	24			1'920
Local publishers	Institutional	1	2	5	6'400	80	80			6'400
Costs for					5'000					5'000
Dissemination	Publication of	1	5	3	9'600	80	120			9'600
Coordination and	Project meetings,	3	5	3	28'800	80	360	9'600	9'600	9'600
Travel expenses					3'500			1'167	1'167	1'167
Total					80'820		904	22'287	24'847	33'687

Total

Total

Activities for each partner Budget 50'000 chf

Work package	Description	Number of	Units	Days	Total cost	Cost per hour	Total hours	Costs per year			
								2022	2023	2024	
Guidelines	Selection of case	2	2	1	2'560	80	32	2'560			
Guidelines	Review of the	2	2	1	2'560	80	32	2'560			
Training	Participating in	2	2	1	2'560	80	32		2'560		
Training	Training for	2	2	1	2'560	80	32		2'560		
Training	Training for	2	2	1	2'560	80	32		2'560		
Local publishers	Relationships	1	3	1	1'920	80	24			1'920	
Local publishers	Institutional	1	2	5	6'400	80	80			6'400	
Costs for					5'000					5'000	
Dissemination	Publication of	1	3	1	1'920	80	24			1'920	
Coordination and	Project meetings,	2	5	3	19'200	80	240	6'400	6'400	6'400	
Travel expenses					3'000			1'000	1'000	1'000	
Total					50'240		528	12'520	15'080	22'640	50'240

Total

Total

Contributions	Institutions	Total cash	Total inkind	Total
	SUPSI (Accademia Dimitri)	60'000.00	20'000.00	80'000.00
	HES-SO (ECAL, HEAD, EDHEA)	60'000.00	20'000.00	80'000.00
	BFH	60'000.00	20'000.00	80'000.00
	ZHdK	60'000.00	20'000.00	80'000.00
	HSLU	30'000.00	20'000.00	50'000.00
	FHNW	60'000.00	20'000.00	80'000.00
	Total contribution Swiss schools of arts	330'000.00	120'000.00	CHF450'000
Request to				CHF348'460
			Total budget	CHF798'460

Month	124		
Per partner 80'000 Local services			
Coordination	480	3.87	
Guidelines	144	1.16	
Training	176	1.42	
Publications	104	0.84	
Total	904	7.29	

Month	124		
Per partner 50'000 Local services (HSLU)			
Coordination	264	2.13	
Guidelines	64	0.52	
Training	96	0.77	
Publications	104	0.84	
Total	528	4.26	

Month	124								
	Centralised services	CCDigitalLaw	SUPSI						Total SUPSI including local and centralised services
Coordination	1680		480	2160	17.42				
Guidelines	2'112	400	144	2656	21.42				
Training	272	400	176	848	0.15				
Publications	456	400	104	960	0.13				
Total	4'520	1'200	904	6624	53.42				

Summary of all partners										
Workpackage	Total SUPSI including local	HES-SO	HKB	BFH	ZHdK	FHNW	HSLU	Total		
Coordination	17.42	3.87	3.87	3.87	3.87	3.87	3.87	2.13	38.90	
Guidelines	21.42	1.16	1.16	1.16	1.16	1.16	1.16	0.52	27.74	
Training	0.15	1.42	1.42	1.42	1.42	1.42	1.42	0.77	8.02	
Publications	0.13	0.84	0.84	0.84	0.84	0.84	0.84	0.84	5.17	
Total	39.11	7.29	7.29	7.29	7.29	7.29	7.29	4.26	79.82	

Open Science for Arts, Design and Music

Table 2. Areas and activities

Area	Specific Activities	Implemented by	Duration
Centralised service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Active involvement of the Swiss schools of ADM - Analysis of a selection of case studies produce with the support of legal advice (expected selection of 10 case studies) - Documentation about research practices in the field of ADM - Production of guidelines - Editing and publication of the guidelines - Production of webinars (3 webinars) - Training and coaching to trainers - Documentation about practices of publishers specialised in ADM in the field of Open Access - Networking with international publishers in the field of ADM to support 3 publications in Open Access - Relationships with DOAJ - Coordination (production of the reports, administrative management of the project, communication within the project, regular meetings) - Communication and dissemination of the project at a national and international level - Institutional website with guidelines, recorded webinars and other documents (June 2023) 	Project team	2022-2024. Possibility to activate specific activities after 2024.
Local services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Definition of a local team - Identifying relevant case studies and best practices (expected 20) - Reviewing of the guidelines and reports - Participating in training 	Local teams	During the project
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training and coaching to researchers - 3 schools involved in the project organize workshops/seminars/courses related to Open Science for students - Relationships with 3 national specialised publishers in the field of ADM (in German, French and Italian) - Implementation of OA in institutional publications 		During the project and beyond 2024

Table 2. Areas and activities

Open Science for Arts, Design and Music

Table 6. Related initiatives

Category	Related initiatives	Notes
Networks	DARIAH: A network to enhance and support digitally enabled research and teaching across the Arts and Humanities https://www.dariah.eu/	Envisioned collaboration
Networks	Humanities at Scale (HaS) can be understood as an add-on to DARIAH . It is set up to improve DARIAH in fostering new and sustaining existing knowledge in digitally enabled research in the arts and humanities: http://has.dariah.eu/	
Networks	Fair Open Access Alliance and FAIR Open Access Publishing https://www.fairopenaccess.org/	Application of the principals related to the FAIR Open Access Publishing
Repository	Data and Service Center for the Humanities (DaSCH) is responsible for the long-term preservation of research data in the Humanities.	
Networks and guidelines	FAQ Diritto d'autore, copyright e licenze aperte per la cultura nel WEB, a cura del Digital Heritage Research Group ICOM ITALIA 2021 / FAQ related to copyright and open licenses designed for museums and cultural institutions	2020-2021 Envisioned collaboration
Networks and guidelines	VWS-AMS Association of Swiss museums (recurrent publication with guidelines and checklists for museums and cultural institutions). One issue was dedicated to copyright ("Copyright: Practical knowledge for museums")	
Open Science	OpenAIRE, participatory initiative to shift scholarly communication toward openness and transparency https://www.openaire.eu/	Envisioned collaboration
Open Science with a thematic approach	Open ScienCe Aeronautic & Air Transport Research https://oscar-h2020.eu/	
Training	FOSTER is a coordination initiative that aims to support different stakeholders, especially young researchers, in adopting open access in the context of the European Research Area (ERA) and in complying with the open access policies and rules of participation set out for Horizon 2020 (H2020). https://www.fosteropenscience.eu/	2017-2019 (foster+)
Infrastructures	EOSC pilot The European Open Science Cloud for Research Pilot Projects https://www.eoscpilot.eu/	2017-2019
Infrastructures	HIRMEOS is going to improve five important publishing platforms for the open access monographs in the SSH and enhance their technical capacities and services, rendering technologies and content interoperable and embedding them fully into the European Open Science Cloud. The platforms participating (OpenEdition Books, OAPEN Library, EKT Open Book Press, Ubiquity Press and Göttingen University Press) will be enriched with tools that enable identification, authentication and interoperability (DOI, ORCID, Fundref), and tools that enrich information and entity extraction (INRIA (N)ERD), the ability to annotate monographs (hypothes.is), and gather usage and alternative metric data. HIRMEOS will also enrich the technical capacities of the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB) https://www.hirmeos.eu/	2017-2019

Infrastructures	The project aims to provide a full-fledged Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) where data, tools, and training are available and accessible for users of SSH data. https://www.sshopencloud.eu/	2019-2022
Software	VRE4EIC. A Europe-wide Interoperable Virtual Research Environment to Empower Multidisciplinary Research Communities and Accelerate Innovation and Collaboration. https://vre4eic.ercim.eu/	2015-2018
	OpenUP. OpenUP addressed key aspects and challenges of the currently transforming science landscape in terms of quality assurance of scientific publications, communication of scientific outputs, and impact assessment with a focus on Open Science. It mapped out and promoted new solutions that better suit the needs of researchers, innovators, the public and funding bodies.	2016-2018
Publications	cognitio. Open-Access-Zeitschrift für Studierende der Rechtswissenschaften. Supported by swissuniversities.	
Publications	e-codices 2017-2020. Virtual manuscript library of Switzerland. Supported by swissuniversities.	
Publications	histHub Phase 2-3. Establishment and operation of a research platform for the historical sciences. Supported by swissuniversities.	
Publications	histHub Phase 4. Networked and standardized data for historical sciences. Supported by swissuniversities.	
Publications	NIE-INE. National Infrastructure for editions. Supported by swissuniversities.	
Publications	NIE-INE Phase 2. National Infrastructure for Editions, Phase 2: From Project to Infrastructure. Supported by swissuniversities.	
Publications	OA-EASI. Open Access for Educational and Applied Sciences in Switzerland. Supported by swissuniversities.	
Publications	SONAR. Future archive of scientific publications. Supported by swissuniversities.	
Publications	SwissCOSS. Specialised Research IT support to the Swiss research academic sector. Supported by swissuniversities.	
Services	Swiss MOOC Service. Switzerland-wide solution for Massive Open Online Courses. Supported by swissuniversities.	
Services	INCIPIT. INCIPIT - Infrastructure Nationale d'un Complément d'Identifiants Pérennes, Interopérables et Traçables. Supported by swissuniversities.	
Services	ASPIRE. Graasp for Open Evidence-Based Research in Digital Education. Supported by swissuniversities.	
Services	Easy FAIR. Supporting the adoption of FAIR and reproducible digital scholarship with Renku. Supported by swissuniversities.	
Services	OA Compliance Check Tool. Open Access Compliance Check Tool. Supported by swissuniversities.	
eScience	Develop SUID. Simple User Interface to the Data and Service Center for the Humanities (DaSCH) database. Supported by swissuniversities.	

eScience	DLCM Phase 2. Massgeschneidertes Forschungsdatenmanagement. Supported by swissuniversities.	
eScience	OLOS.swiss. Supported by swissuniversities.	
Legal advice	DMLawTool. Guiding Tool for researchers to address legal aspects in data management. Supported by swissuniversities.	Envisioned collaboration
eScience	INCIPIT-CRIS. Infrastructure Nationale d'un Complément d'Identifiants Pérennes, Interopérables et Traçables – Current Research Information System. Supported by swissuniversities.	
eScience	Materials Cloud. Materials Cloud as an open, international, and fully FAIR repository of computational data and workflows. Supported by swissuniversities.	
eScience	openRDM.swiss. A National Platform for FAIR Research Data Management and Analysis. Supported by swissuniversities.	
eScience	SELVEDAS. Service for Large Volume Experiment-Data Analysis utilising Supercomputing and Cloud Infrastructures. Supported by swissuniversities.	
Training	Summer School. Summer School on Open Data and Open Access for Early-Career Researchers from Swiss Universities. Supported by swissuniversities.	
eScience	SwissDAcS. Unterstützung und Infrastruktur für wissenschaftliches Datenmanagement. Supported by swissuniversities.	
eScience	Arbeitsinfrastruktur für das Management von Daten und Forschungsinformationen. Supported by swissuniversities.	
eScience	SWISSUbase. A Modular Research Information and Data Archiving Solution. Supported by swissuniversities.	
Infrastructures	EOSC-ELCH. Swiss EOSC-EGI Link. Supported by swissuniversities.	
Infrastructures	SLSP-Real+. Realisierung Swiss Library Service Platform. Supported by swissuniversities.	
Infrastructures	Swiss edu-ID. The academic identity made in Switzerland. Supported by swissuniversities.	
Services	SWITCH edu-ID. Digital identity for the Swiss university environment. Service supported by swissuniversities.	
Services	CCdigitallaw. Competence Center in Digital Law: for legal issues relating to digitalisation. Service supported by swissuniversities.	Envisioned collaboration
Services	e-manuscripta.ch . New module for the creation of transcriptions. Service supported by swissuniversities.	
Services	SWITCHengines. Tailored storage and virtual machines for the academic community. Service supported by swissuniversities.	

Table 6. Related initiatives

Open Science for Arts, Design and Music

Table 9. Local team and activities

University	OS strategy and OA repository	OA office-r	School	Project reference person	Other collaborator(s)	Existing local activity	Planned local activity
SUPSI	OS strategy: https://www2.supsi.ch/cms/openscience/	Service Research and Innovation	Dipartimento Ambiente Costruzioni e Design	♀ Iolanda Pensa	♀ Loredana Alberti	Publications Artichoke (printed and digital publication) https://issuu.com/supsi_comunicazione_visiva Cross-media lab (a transdisciplinary collaboration and performance) Online videos and performances	Training for researchers, teacher and collaborators
	InStory: https://repository.supsi.ch/		Accademia Dimitri (Research Axes 7: The Role of Arts in Life and Well-Being of Citizens in Their Communities)	♂ Demis Quadri			Training for students and researchers
HES-SO	OS strategy: https://openscience.hes-so.ch/fr/open-science-14415.html	Open HES-SO (♀ Isabelle Lucas)	ECAL	♂ Davide Fornari	♀ Yoo-Mi Steffen (librarian) ♀ Margherita Bianchi (research assistant)	OA publications: - DSGDM : Digital Strategies in Genre-Defining Magazines https://hesso.tind.io/record/4918?ln=en	Training for MA students and researchers within the module "Training to Research"
	Arodes: https://arodes.hes-so.ch/		EDHEA	♀ Federica Martini	♀ Kate Espasandin (librarian)	OA publications: Blackout Magazine, a paper-based and online journal	Training for students (Master level) and researchers
			HEAD – Genève	♂ Anthony Masure	♀ Claire Medri Vignola (documentaliste)	OA publications: - ISSUE-Journal, an online journal on art and design : https://issue-journal.ch - HEAD – Publishing, 3 books (Manifesto) released on April 2021 on OA with several formats: https://www.hesge.ch/head/evenement/2021/lancement-head-publishing - Online Archival on HAL-SHS: https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/HEAD-GENEVE/browse/latest-publications - Partnerships with OA publishing houses: Naïma, MétisPresses, Presses du Réel	- Training for MA students and researchers within the module "Training to Research" - OA information point + individual coaching service. - Information events on OA. - Development of OA books in various digital formats. - Archiving of research project databases and websites to ensure their longevity.

ZHdK	<p>OA Policy: https://www.zhdk.ch/file/live/a6/a6d5038632f97862b2ca983afc92ed5847250c5d/zhdk-open-access_policy_en.pdf</p> <p>ZOPAR: https://www.zeno.do.org/communiti/es/zhdk/?page=1&size=20</p> <p>Research Data Management Policy: https://www.zhdk.ch/file/live/ff/ff05e953c7ff71a9a00080f090f6d23245e648a2/rd_policy_zhdk_201911.pdf</p> <p>Media Archive: https://medienarc.hiv.zhdk.ch/</p>	Research Affairs Office (♀) Jasna Zwimpfer Open Access Services (♀) Esther Zaugg	—	♀ Jasna Zwimpfer, ♀ Esther Zaugg	Open Access Repository and Gold Open Access Funds: https://www.zhdk.ch/en/miz/open-access-1823	<p>Two to three pilot studies with the aim to produce multimedia Open Science research publications</p> <p>Yearly Open Science event with experts</p> <p>Dissemination of centrally developed guidelines and trainings to researchers at ZHdK</p>
Hochschule Luzern – Design & Kunst	<p>OA strategy: https://www.hslu.ch/en/luceme-university-of-applied-sciences-and-arts/campus/libraries/repository/</p> <p>Lory: https://www.zhblu.zern.ch/dienstleistungen/forschen-publizieren/</p>	<p>Simone Rosenkranz (OA); (♀) Andrea Eichholzer (Digital Agenda)</p>	—	♀ Rachel Mader	<p>Open Access Repository and Gold Open Access Funds: https://www.zhdk.ch/en/miz/open-access-1823</p> <p>Infrastructures/Agreements: SCOSS (DOAB & OAPEN, PKP, OpenCitations), Knowledge Unlatched, Open Library of Humanities, Cambridge University Press, Sage, Taylor&Francis, Elsevier, Springer Nature, Wiley</p> <p>Local infrastructures for Green Open Access and Research Data Management: ZOPAR & Media Archive</p> <p>OA-Journals: OnCurating, Wind Tunnel Bulletin, Art Education Research</p> <p>Portal Partner Research Catalogue: https://www.researchcatalogue.net</p> <p>Research Data Management: https://www.zhdk.ch/en/miz/research-data-management-7111</p>	<p>Clarifications and negotiations on publishing OA with chosen publishers</p> <p>Including OA governance in the re-organisation of the library services</p> <p>Evaluating formats of publishing with reference to OA databases</p> <p>Training students, lecturers and other staff members concerning OA</p> <p>Evaluating the sustainability of data management with reference to internal storage of it</p>
BFH	<p>OA policy: https://www.droppb ox.com/s/1n4h7e gw6z1pgl8/Open_Access_Policy_EN.pdf?dl=0</p>	Open Access Office (♀) Desirée Stalder	HKB	♂ Robert Lzicar	<p>BFH: - Richtlinien zur Förderung von wissenschaftlichen Open Access Publikationen an der BFH - Partnerships with publishing houses (MDPI, Cambridge University Press,</p>	<p>OA information point + individual coaching service</p> <p>Information events on OA.</p> <p>Best practice award for OA publishing (including presentation).</p>

	<p>Arbor: https://www.droppbox.com/s/158ba4d9vid8un/Repository/%20Policy.pdf?dl=0</p>					<p>SAGE, Taylor&Francis, Elsevier and Springer) - Online consultations - OS Strategie (under development) HKB: - Partnerships with publishing houses (Argus, Scheidegger & Spiess, transcript) - Data Management Expert: Claudio Baccagaluppi - SNF-Sinergia Participatory Knowledge Practices in Analogue and Digital Image Archives (Institute of Design Research) - Ehrenreich Collection (Institut Interpretation) - Project Tonkünstlerverein (Institut Interpretation) - Datenbanken des Institut Interpretation</p>	<p>- Support for books to be published in OA. - Teaching format on OA/OS for Master students (at Y.institute). - Workshop/Symposium on handling large databases.</p>
<p>FHNW</p>	<p>OA policy: https://www.fhnw.ch/de/die-fhnw/bibliothek/en/open-access IRF: https://irf.fhnw.ch/</p>	<p>♂ Jörg Wiesel</p>	<p>HGK</p>	<p>♂ Michael Renner</p>	<p>♀ Tabea Lurk ♂ Christoph Moor ♀ Jane Haller</p>	<p>- Guidelines FHNW for OA policy https://www.fhnw.ch/de/die-fhnw/bibliothek/en/open-access - IRF Database for Research Output and Filmanimation of the MHS and HGK through the Mediathek/Library of the HGK/MHS - Cielab.ch: Projectdatabase of the Critical-Icono-Entnography-Lab - Critical by Design: OA Publication published by transcript publishing</p>	<p>- Training for Researchers and for MA students - Information events on OA at the Mediathek/Library of the HGK/MHS FHNW - Development of OA publications in analogue and digital formats for the HGK/MHS FHNW. - Support for the Archiving of research projects in the IRF FHNW to ensure their impact.</p>

Table 9. Local team and activities

Open Science for Arts, Design and Music

Table 10. OS and OA requirements of relevant grant-makers in the fields of ADM

Grant-makers supporting arts and design	OS and OA requirements
Swiss National Science Foundation - Research grants	OA and Open Data
Swiss National Science Foundation - Agora grants	
Swiss National Science Foundation - Publication grants	OA
Creative Europe Network	
European Union	OA and Open Data
Federal office of culture	
Network of European Museum Organisations (NEMO)	
Pro Helvetia	
Cantonal departments of culture	(Open government data)
Foundations such as Ernst Göhner Stiftung, Hasler Stiftung, Gebert Rüt Stiftung, Migros Fondation Nestlé pour l'Art, IKEA Stiftung Schweiz, Berner Design Stiftung	
Cultural institutions	(Open government data)

Table 10. OS and OA requirements of relevant grant-makers in the fields of ADM

Open Science for Arts, Design and Music

Table 11. OA requirements of a selection of relevant publications in the field of ADM

Journals	Access	Peer-review	DOAJ	License	Link
Journal for artistic research (JAR)	Online	√		All rights reserved	https://www.jar-online.net/
Art Research Journal	Online		√	CC BY-NC-SA	https://periodicos.ufrn.br/artresearchjournal
Design science (Cambridge University Press)	Online		√		https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/design-science
Design Issues (MIT Press)	Online	√			https://direct.mit.edu/desi
Sciences du Design	Online	√			http://www.sciences-du-design.org/index.php/sdd
A/I/S/Design (Italy)	Online	√	√		http://www.aisdesign.org/aisd/
ICOM-CC	Online	√	√	All rights reserved	http://www.icom-cc.org/360/publications/icom-cc-publications-online/#.YD4Zq11ueZw
She Ji: The Journal of Design, Economics, and Innovation (Elsevier)	Online	√	√	CC BY-NC-SA	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/she-ji-the-journal-of-design-economics-and-innovation/
Back Office	Online and print	√		CC BY-NC-SA	http://www.revue-backoffice.com/
conferences with OA publications ICDHS - International Conferences on Design History and Studies	Online and print	√			http://www.ub.edu/icdhs/
MetisPresses (Swiss publisher based in Geneva)	Online and print	√			https://www.metispresses.ch/fr
Triest Verlag (Swiss publisher based in Zurich and St. Gallen) – book series: “Visual Archives”	Online and print	√			https://www.triest-verlag.ch/en/
Casagrande (Swiss publisher based in Bellinzona)	Online and print	√			http://www.edizionicasagrande.com/
Società svizzera di studi teatrali	Online and print				https://www.mimos.ch/sgtk/

International Federation for Theatre Research	Online				https://www.iftr.org/
Society for Artistic Research	Online				https://societyforartisticresearch.org/
International Platform for Performer Training	Online				https://performertrainingplatform.wordpress.com/
"Culture teatrali"	Online				https://cultureteatrali.dar.unibo.it/
"Studies in Theatre and Performance"	Online				https://www.tandfonline.com/toc/rstp20/current
"Theatre Research International"	Online				https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/theatre-research-international
Società Svizzera di Musicologia	Online				https://www.smg-ssm.ch/smg-ssm/publikationen/publikationen/schweizer-jahrbuch-fuer-musikwissenschaft/
Peter Lang Verlagsgruppe	Online and print				https://www.peterlang.com/
Open Book Publishers	Online				https://www.openbookpublishers.com/
"Rivista italiana di Musicologia"	Online				https://www.sidm.it/ojs/index.php/ridm

Table 11. OA requirements of a selection of relevant publications in the field of ADM

Open Science for Arts, Design and Music

Table 22. Specific project objectives, activities and deliverables

Specific project objectives	Activities and deliverables
Monitoring of research practices in the fields of ADM.	- Guidelines
Monitoring of the practices of publishers specialised in ADM in the field of Open Access.	
Providing guidelines to researchers on how to publish in Green and Gold Open Access and deal with common problems.	- Guidelines - 6 trainings for researchers - formats TBD (March-April 2023, October 2023) - 3 webinars (March-April 2023, October 2023)
Including Open Science (i.e. copyright management, open licenses, multimedia formats, reviewing processes) within students' curricula	- 3 schools involved in the project organize workshops/seminars/courses related to Open Science for their students (March-April 2023, October 2023)
Implementing Open Access among institutional publications.	- 70% of institutional publications in Green or Gold Open Access (June 2024)
Negotiating Open Access with publishers (Green and Gold Road) at a national and international level.	- 3 international journals in Green or Gold Open Access (June 2024) - 3 national publishers in Green or Gold Open Access options (June 2024)
Guaranteeing the viability of the project once the funding from the OS programme stops	- Project structured in centralised services (2022-2024) and local services (meant to continue after the end of the project) - Training and coaching of local teams. Involvement of Swiss networks for the follow up of the project

Table 22. Specific project objectives, activities and deliverables

Open Science for Arts, Design and Music

Table 23. Problems and envisioned topics for the guidelines

Problem	Envisioned topic for the guidelines
Necessity of producing research based on documents and images of archives and of including these documents within the research outputs (publications, exhibitions, catalogues, multimedia installations...).	Managing third parties rights for content in the public domain (70 years after the death of the author); legal restrictions for images, related to heritage management; rights related to reproductions; fees; restrictions related to digital publications.
Necessity of producing research based on contemporary documents, images, audio and video and of including these documents within the research outputs (publications, exhibitions, catalogues, prototypes, artworks, multimedia installations...).	Working with contemporary archives. Managing third parties rights for contemporary multimedia content (audio recordings, video, images...), freedom of panorama; finding content with open licenses, requisitioning authorizations or content under open licenses; fees.
	Release of content under open licenses (CC0, CC BY and CC BY-SA) and request of authorisations to release content under open licenses.
	Copyright management for collaborative productions; involvement of children and people with disabilities in performances and multimedia installations.
Necessity of producing multimedia research outputs produced by action-research and practice-based research (publications, exhibitions, catalogues, websites, multimedia installations, artworks...).	Managing third parties rights for digital dissemination, printed publications, catalogues, exhibitions, multimedia installations, design, performances, artworks.
	Managing the peer-review process and ethical issues for multimedia research outputs.
Preserving authors' rights and third parties rights.	Different modalities of disseminating research outputs with different forms of OA.
Production of a Data management plan for research proposals to be submitted to SNF and other grant-maker.	Models of data management plans.
Archiving data and content	FAIR data, data management and archiving third parties content. Issues related to media libraries and data repositories.
Necessity of training researchers to allow them to produce works they can disseminate.	Syllabus for researchers in copyright management, open licenses, open access, production of a data management plan.
Necessity of training students to allow them to produce works they can disseminate.	Syllabus for students in copyright management and open licenses.
Reaching maximum circulation of outputs.	Different modalities of disseminating research outputs and producing knowledge transfer among the targeted disciplinary communities and among society at large.
Persisting value of printed outputs.	Managing OA combined with printed outputs.
Incapacity of current institutional repositories to include multimedia formats	Documenting pilot projects. Possibility of using different repositories or producing peer-reviewed institutional websites or websites produced in collaboration with publishers.
Specialised publishers and journals in the fields of ADM are not in OA or included among DOAJ	Documenting pilot projects. Model of letters.

Table 23. Problems and envisioned topics for the guidelines

Open Science for Arts, Design and Music

Profiles of the team members

Noa Bacchetta (b. 1972) studied law at the University of Lucerne. He is active as an independent lawyer. He was a research assistant at the ZHAW (2005–2008). Since 2007, lecturer for law and professional studies at F + F Schule für Kunst und Design.

CCdigitallaw (www.ccdigitallaw.ch<<http://www.ccdigitallaw.ch>>) is a national Competence Center in Digital Law that supports Swiss Higher Education Institutions (students, academic and administrative staff) in dealing with legal questions related to the digitization process and the use of digital technologies. In particular it focuses on aspects related to copyright, data protection and licensing. Through its online platform the center offers a detailed knowledge base, FAQs, a wide range of on-and offline training activities and an advising service.

CCdigitallaw is currently operated by the eLearning Lab (<https://www.usi.ch/it/universita/info/elab>) of the Università della Svizzera italiana (www.usi.ch<<http://www.usi.ch>>) and is the result of a project funded within the P-5 programme “Scientific Information” of swissuniversities.

Anna Picco-Schwendener is a postdoctoral researcher at the Faculty of Communication, Culture and Society of the Università della Svizzera italiana (USI) and a scientific collaborator at USI’s eLearning Lab. As part of her duties she teaches Online Communication Design and E-Government and is in charge of the CCdigitallaw project (www.ccdigitallaw.ch<<http://www.ccdigitallaw.ch>>) as well as of other projects like DMLawTool, MAPAW, MARKS and “Machu Picchu, seen through the eyes of Fernando Asteste”. Furthermore, she is part of the operative unit of the Lugano Living Lab (<https://luganolivinglab.ch>).

Suzanna Marazza is a collaborator at Università della Svizzera italiana (USI)’s eLearning Lab (<http://www.elearninglab.org>) and works as legal consultant on several projects dealing with digital law - ranging from copyright to data protection, especially within academia. She works for the project CCdigitallaw (<https://ccdigitallaw.ch/index.php/english>) which is a competence center in digital law for Swiss Higher Education Institutions, doing workshops and responding to requests in Italian, German, French and English related to copyright, licensing and data protection.

Davide Fornari (Mantua 1979) is associate professor at ECAL / University of Art and Design Lausanne (HES-SO), where he leads the Applied Research and Development sector. He coordinates the scientific commission of the Arts and Design competence center of HES-SO / University of Applied Sciences and Arts Western Switzerland. He is vice-president of Swiss Design Network since 2021. He has been main applicant or coordinator of the projects “Swiss Graphic Design and Typography Revisited”, “Culture and Safety in Africa”, “The Sources of Jan Tschichold’s The New Typography”, “Casa Zentner in Zurich: an Italian Villa in Switzerland”, “Re-programmed art: an open manifesto”, all aimed at producing open access outputs and resources, that have become reference works in the field. Previously he was a tenured teacher-researcher at SUPSI. Trained as an architect, he holds a Ph.D. in Design Sciences from University luav of Venice.

Iolanda Pensa (Geneva 1975) is senior researcher at SUPSI University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland, head of the research area “Culture and Territory” (Laboratory of visual culture/Department for Environment Constructions and Design), board member of SUPSI, and actively involved in the implementation of Open Science as consultant for SUPSI Research and Innovation team. She was principal investigator of the projects “Wikipedia Primary School: Providing on Wikipedia the information necessary to complete the cycle of primary education in the languages used by the different education systems”, “Case-based research for education”, “Swiss Foundations and Open Licenses”, “The Alps on Wikipedia” and “Culture and Safety in Africa” with all the research documentation on the Wikimedia projects. Previously she was scientific director of the Moleskine Foundation for the project “Share Your Knowledge: Creative Commons and Wikipedia for cultural institutions” and “WikiAfrica: Increasing the quality and quantity of African content on Wikipedia” (which produced over 30’000 contributions to the Wikimedia projects with the involvement of volunteers and over 100 cultural institutions, archives and museums releasing content with an open licenses CC0, CC BY and CC BY-SA). As a volunteers she is an active contributor of Wikipedia since 2006, member of Wikimedia Italia and Wikimedia CH, active in the implementation of the contest Wiki Loves Monuments and in increasing the documentation of cultural heritage on Wikipedia and the Wikimedia projects, organizer of Wikimania Esino Lario 2016, the Wikipedia world conference in a mountain village in the Alps, chair of the Wikimania International Committee since 2017 and since 2020 president of Wikimedia Italia. Art historian, she holds a Ph.D. in Social anthropology and ethnography at the EHESS in Paris and in Territorial government and planning at the Politecnico di Milano.

Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra works as the Open Science Officer of DARIAH-EU where she is responsible for fostering and implementing policies and practices related to the open dissemination of research results in the arts and humanities. Her advocacy activities include providing workshops, webinars, and other training activities on a regular basis covering topics like publications in Open Access, open and FAIR data management, Citizen Science, or collaborative research practices. She is also involved in European infrastructure-building projects such as OpenAire Advance, OPERAS-P and TRIPLE. She is co-chair of the Research Data Management Working Group of DARIAH and editor-in-chief of the OpenMethods platform. She received her PhD in Cultural Linguistics and also has a background in scholarly communication.

Berlin, 14th of May 2021

Subject: Letter of support, project “Open Science for Arts, Design and Music (OS-ADM)”

Dear Members of the Selection Committee,

On behalf of the Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH), we would like to formally express our support for the project “Open Science for Arts, Design and Music (OS-ADM)”, in response to the call Swiss Universities Open Science Program I. DARIAH is strongly committed to the promotion of open responsible research practices. It actively seeks to bridge the gap between principles of Open Science, research ethics and actual research practices in a wide variety of arts and humanities disciplines. We work towards implementing open research and publication workflows also in research communities that do not have developed corresponding digital or computational capacities yet.

DARIAH as a pan-European infrastructure for arts and humanities scholars supports digital research and teaching and directly connects several hundreds of scholars and dozens of research facilities, tools and services in currently 19 European DARIAH member countries, one DARIAH observer country and an extended network of cooperating partners including partner institutions beyond Europe. Optimising the environment for arts and humanities research necessarily involves strong and strategic support facilitating the transition towards open scholarship in the humanities. We have taken on leadership in the area of Open Science for the arts and humanities, participating in key policy bodies like the European Open Science Policy Platform, devising projects and instruments of our own to make Open Science a reality in the arts and humanities. As a true commitment to achieve this goal, DARIAH takes a key role in the development of the SSH component of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) within the Horizon 2020 project "Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud" (SSHOC).

As a third major component of strengthening the open agenda for arts and humanities research in addition to the infrastructural investment and involvement in policy making, our organisation supports the deeper and broader adoption of open research practices by regularly organising training opportunities of different kinds, e.g., winter/summer schools, webinars, or workshops as well as through our DARIAH Campus platform that hosts and brings together training materials that facilitate the implementation of digital and open research methods within the arts and humanities domain. The DARIAH masterclasses encourage researchers to produce open contents: open data, open lexical data or open educational resources. Besides that, we both produce and contribute to a number of platforms and projects offering open science advocacy and training such as OpenAire, OPERAS, PARTHENOS, FOSTER, OpenCon or the Open Science MOOC. As contributors to these projects, we have the opportunity to (co)create suitable discipline-dependent training materials for the humanities research communities and integrate them with the global Open Science training curricula.

As part of this partnership, our Open Science officer looks forward to working with colleagues from the “Open Science for Arts, Design and Music OS-ADM” project to firmly ground open research practices in the arts disciplines and tackle domain-specific issues (such as special challenges in Open Access publishing, facilitating reuse of cultural heritage collections as open research data, implementing the Heritage Data Reuse Charter for this purpose etc.). Besides, DARIAH-EU offers possibilities for collaboration and hosting capacities for the training materials to be developed within the framework of the project on DARIAH Campus. Finally, DARIAH-EU can spread the word about the project outputs through the Open Science focused DARIAH channels such as the DARIAH Open blog or the OpenMethods platform.

We look forward to working with you and all other members of this partnership to advance this important project.

Yours sincerely,

Jennifer Edmond
President, Board of Directors,
DARIAH ERIC

Frank Fischer
Director, Board of Directors,
DARIAH ERIC

Toma Tasovac
Director, Board of Directors,
DARIAH ERIC

ECAL

Ecole cantonale d'art de Lausanne

Davide Fornari

Associate Professor

Head of R&D

5, avenue du Temple

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T +41 44 267 71 71
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www.prohelvetia.ch

Zurich, 27.05.2021

Lettre of recommendation for « Open Science for Arts, Design and Music»

Dear Madam, Dear Sir,

Professor Davide Fornari has approached the Swiss Arts Council Pro Helvetia with a project proposal aimed to be submitted to swissuniversities' Open Science Program.

The Open Science for Arts, Design and Music proposal aims to tackle the complex issue of distribution of artworks in the public domain by supporting Swiss Art Universities to implement Open Science.

Facilitating access to artworks and allowing them to meet their audience is a central mission for the Swiss Art Council Pro Helvetia. We therefore encourage further research in Open Source and Open Access to bring concrete and innovative solutions to this issue.

Yours sincerely,

Jérôme Benoit
Head of Visual Arts & Design Sector / Deputy
Director

jbenoit@prohelvetia.ch
+41 44 267 71 78

SARN Swiss Artistic Research Network

SARN – Swiss Artistic Research Network, www.sarn.ch, info@sarn.ch

Swissuniversities
Effingerstrasse 15
3001 Bern

Letter of Support - «Open Science for Arts, Design and Music OS-ADM

To whom it may concern

We are pleased to confirm our interest and support regarding the application «Open Science for Arts, Design and Music OS-ADM».

Open Science and Open Access are issues of fundamental importance to the arts, but the challenges are great and we are only just beginning to address them. We are therefore very pleased with this submission, which aims to address some of the most central concerns in a joint nationwide effort.

SARN is connected to the project in several ways: as a dialogue partner on issues concerning artistic research, as a place for dissemination of the results, and as a link to the national and international community.

We believe that the proposed project addresses a virulent issue for the arts sector and are happy to support the research group in addressing this wherever possible.

Your sincerely

Markus Schwander, Co-President SARN

swissuniversities
Effingerstrasse 15
PO Box
3001 Bern

Zurich, 11 May 2021

Letter of Intent – swissuniversities proposal «Open Science for Arts, Design and Music OS-ADM»

To Whom It May Concern

With this letter we are pleased to offer our support for the swissuniversities application «Open Science for Arts, Design and Music OS-ADM».

The project promises a great contribution to our network and stakeholders. We also see a major benefit in this collaboration, since all members of our network are involved. The gap as stipulated in the application is also of great concern to us. We the SDN regularly publish our conference proceedings and publication with Open Access licenses and therefore see great potential in the efforts of this project.

The international network and dissemination that will be established through the project will cement the leading position of Swiss arts schools within the open-source publishing community. We confirm that our network will support the framework of the tasks described in the project plan and will disseminate the activities within the network of schools.

Yours sincerely

Prof. Dr. Sarah Owens
President SDN

Berne, May 12, 2021

To whom it may concern

I am very pleased to write a letter of recommendation for the joint application of all Swiss schools of art and design, led by the Scuola universitaria professionale della Svizzera italiana (SUPSI).

As the head of design promotion at the Federal Office of Culture, I would like to underline the importance of the primary action line of their application – creating alternative forms of publications. It is more essential than ever in our common field.

Furthermore, as assessed in their dossier, it is important to find new ways to pass on knowledge and images in our ever increasing information age. Therefore, accessibility seems, paradoxically, to be increasingly difficult to reach, due to the expanding digital paradigm and its yet unknown limits.

Their secondary action line, to participate to international initiatives, is equally important, and support the same mission as the Federal Office for Culture, i.e. to make Switzerland an influencing platform for MDA excellency.

Many of the works selected for the Swiss Design Awards exhibition come from the schools of art and design applying to Swiss universities call. Therefore, it seems essential to me to endorse the applicants in supporting their researchers and therefore enhancing the quality of the designers that begin their career with a degree from one of these high quality institutions.

Yours sincerely,

Anna Niederhäuser

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Berne, 27 April 2021

Letter of acknowledgement

To whom it may concern,

The SNSF was approached by Prof. Davide Fornari representing the applicants of a project proposal to be submitted to swissuniversities' Open Science Program. The proposal aims at supporting the "*Swiss disciplinary field of art and design in implementing Open Science and in particular the swissuniversities Open Access action plan 2021-2024*".

As the SNSF's open access coordinator I can confirm that the issue addressed by the proposal is relevant for the advancement of open access in general and the Swiss open access landscape in particular. The envisaged results could be of interest and use to the SNSF and our efforts to support SNSF grantees in all disciplines to ensure open access to their scholarly publications.

Yours sincerely,

Tobias Philipp

Scientific Officer, Coordinator Open Access